

**QUANTIFYING AND CHARACTERIZING SOLID WASTE OF MAJOR DUMPSITES
IN THE OTUOKE COMMUNITY**

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ABSTRACTS

Nigeria, the most populous black nation with the largest solid waste generation in Africa is challenged with waste management and environmental hygiene. This also reflected in the waste management capacity of the Otuoke (both on campus and in the community); thereby constituting environmental pollution because tons of refuse are seen littered within Otuoke. This work seeks to quantify and characterized solid waste generation within Otuoke, Bayelsa State in order to provide information for solid waste management. The waste samples were collected after 24hours of clearing of the dumpsite for 5 days at the intervals of 15days within four months. The total weight of waste generated in Otuoke from the sample collected is estimated to be 3083 kg; where the average waste produced per day is 616.6 kg and one person deposit 0.85kg/capita/day. 250kg of Fourteen (14) Solid waste samples were characterized into two categories: Organic Waste (OW) which is made up; Wood wastes, Food waste, Manure, Garden waste, and Inorganic Waste (IW) which are Tin/metals, Polythene, Paper, Hair, Rubber/plastic, Glass Baby Diapers, Battery, Hospital waste, Foam/floater. It was discovered that IW with a total weight of 131.504kg and 52.61% is higher than OW which has a total weight of 118.496kg with 47.39%, however food waste of OW rewasroorders.23% which is the highest of the all the fourteen solid waste characterized, and rubber/plastic 18.82% is the highest in IW. More dumpsites should be adequately positioned to meet the demand of increasing population and sensitization its usage, waste should be characterized, the organic wastes to turned to organic fertilizer then rubber/plastic and polythene should be recycled

Keywords:

Solid Waste, Characterization, Organic Waste, Inorganic Waste, Otuoke

INTRODUCTION

The population explosion in Nigeria has become a major concern to the environmentalist; being the most populous black nation in the world and generating the largest solid waste in Africa [1]. Despite a host of policies and regulations, solid waste management in the country is assuming alarming proportions with each passing day [2]. Today as waste is a major problem that needs to be solved as urgently as possible rather than being considered a resource. Nigeria generates more than 32 million tons of solid waste annually, out of which only 20-30% is collected [3]. This also true in Bayelsa state, particularly Otuoke a community in the Ogbia Local Government Area of the state, were rising in the population of the enrollment of the students into the Federal University of Otuoke which boost the community's economic strength that encourages many business minds and scholars to settle on campus and the community resulting winning population that has laid a burden on the waste management capacity of the Otuoke (both the campus and the community); thereby constituting environmental pollution in the community where tons of refuse are seen littered everywhere causing diverse environmental problems.

Pollution is becoming a challenge because of the inadequate disposal of waste. Waste is considered as a worthless or defective object that is discarded after primary use [4]. It was further added by [5] that waste is any material or product that is useless to the producer, this scholar generally agrees that waste is the useless by-product of human activities [5,6]. The findings of [7] pointed out that, wastes are materials that people would want to dispose of even when payments are required for their disposal. Although waste is an essential product of human activities, it is also the result of inefficient production processes whose continuous generation is a loss of vital resources [8].

There are different types of waste namely; hazardous (house and business hazardous) non-hazardous, gaseous, liquid, and solid waste. Solid waste is the core of the study is referred to as is a moveable solid object which is useless to the owner and wishes to dispose of. It is non-soluble material ranging from municipal garbage to industrial wastes containing complex and sometimes hazardous substances. [2] Solid waste can be classified into two broad categories biodegradable solid waste and non-biodegradable solid waste. Biodegradable wastes are those wastes that can be easily decomposed by natural processes ranging from food remnants to leaves from trees, cotton wool, clothes, banana peels, which he and referred to as Organic Solid waste (OSW) that includes agricultural waste, household food waste, human and animal waste [9]. Non-biodegradable wastes are those wastes that cannot be broken down or decomposed by natural processes. They can however be recycled or reused. Such wastes include bottles, glasses, plastics, cans, wrappings of all kinds, nylon bags, metals, needles, and syringes. Solid wastes can also be classified based on their level of environmental contamination that is whether they are hazardous or non-hazardous to both man and the environment [10,11] The sources from which wastes are generated can also be used to classify wastes.

Reckless disposal of municipal solid waste (MSW) has led to blockage of sewers and drainage networks and choking of water bodies which leads to flooding. Most of the wastes are generated by households and in some cases, by local industries, artisans, and traders which litter the immediate surroundings. Improper collection and disposal of municipal wastes are leading to an environmental catastrophe as the country currently lacks adequate budgetary provisions for the implementation of integrated waste management programs across the States [3]. The major problem here is that nobody wants to think of waste but the fact that it is a pressing concern in this modern society where changing lifestyles increases disposable materials. An increase in disposable plastics and polythene materials for packaging goods give rise to new waste disposal problems. Some of these materials are non-biodegradable and when give rise to air pollution burnt. The thought of an increase in the rate at which waste is generated is 70% as compared to 30% of effective management and disposal methods [3] are provoking; the offensive odors cannot be taken for granted. This degrades the environment of its aesthetics and even causes diseases.

There this work seeks to evaluate and enumerate the character of waste within Otuoke, Bayelsa State, and gather the information that will help in planning how to reduce the effect of waste on the environment and public health. The need for a reliable study on the effect of waste generated justifies the rising need for the research. This study is believed to bridge the gap created by inadequate research on the impact of waste generated. The environmental impacts of waste generated in Otuoke must be discovered to enlighten individuals, students, scientists, government, and other operatives on the subject of concern to know the impacts waste generated has on the environment when it is not managed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in selected five major dumpsites in Otuoke, Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria, which is geographically located at 442.418N 6 19'44.472E where Federal University Otuoke is sited as seen in fig 1. The town is located 21 kilometers south of the State capital which is Yenagoa in a humid tropical wetland area with a mean annual rainfall of about 2539 mm and an average temperature of 26.2°C. It has a population of over 18040 occupants, especially during the academic session where make 11,040 people [12] and 7,000 people for the community of Otuoke [13]. Two major dumpsites from the community and three from the university community (boys and girls hostels) totaling five dumpsites were used for the study.

Fig 1: GPS Showing Otuoke and the Federal University Otuoke

Geographical Positioning of Sample Sites

The geographical coordinates of the sample's locations were obtained using Google Global Positioning System (GPS) during the fieldwork activities. The first dump site was found opposite St, Stephen Anglican Church, Otuoke with a geographical location of 4.787287 latitudes and 6.311433 longitudes, and the second dumpsite is located opposite Osasuma lodge and adjacent to University Baptist Church Otuoke; has the geographical location of 4.800087 latitude and longitudes which are 1.1 miles (1.77 kilometers) apart. On the university community (Campus), out of the three dumpsites one is sited in Girl's Hostel geographical with the location of 4.787287 latitudes and 6.311433 longitudes, and two in Boy's Hostels; Block A and B, with the geographical location of 4.787287 latitudes and 6.311433 longitudes. Most disposition of waste is done individually by residents hence reducing the average amount of waste that goes into the dumpsites.

Fig 2: GSP of Otuoke dumpsites

Fig 3: GSP Campus dumpsites

Data Collection

The selected method was based on an on-error-the-spot assessment. Where waste samples were collected after 24hours of clearing of the dumpsite for 5 days at the intervals of 15days within four months. A sampled region of the waste was taken with a waste bin with known weight and volume at four random corners and weighed. The waste was categorized into Fourteen (14) categories, which were; Wood wastes, Food waste, Manure, Tin/metals,

Polythene, Paper, Hair, Rubber/plastic, Glass Baby Diapers, Battery, Garden waste (grasses), Hospital waste, Foam/floater For characterization purposes, each 5kg waste sampled was sorted manually into separate bags for each respective sample. The wastes are collected from 5 recognized dumpsites some of which are presented in figures 4-7

Fig 4: Dumpsite 1

Fig 5: Dumpsite 2

Figure 6: Dumpsite 3

Figure 7: Dumpsite 4

Equipment Used

The equipment used for the collection of the samples are as follows: Shovel, Electronic kitchen Scale, Traffic cone, Rake, Large tarps, Hand broom, Umbrella, Tape, Personal gear (Overalls, Latex gloves, Rubber boots, Disposable facemask), Water, Soap and Disinfectants, Google GPS.

Sampling Methods

A designated area for the waste analysis was clean, disinfected, and demarcated using visible traffic cones, especially the ones that are close to the street, to ensure the safety of the researcher and the assistants from vehicles, including the waste disposal trucks that randomly entered the dumpsite. Sampled solid waste was collected once per day on five different days at the interval of 15days, from the five major dumpsites at random within the space of four months that is from September to December 2021. Large tarps were spread on the area of collection to avoid contamination while sorting the solid waste. The waste was categorized into five storage bags and was labeled according to the dumpsites. An electronic kitchen scale was used to weigh the samples. All containers within the collected waste sample, such as capped jars, paper bags, and plastic bags were emptied of their contents. The weighing was done before and after loading the bags with the sorted wastes. The initial and final readings were recorded, and then the accurate weight is ascertained through weighing rechecked for accuracy. The volume of the bags was known and the volume of waste was calculated approximately using tape leading to find the density of each bag this was projected to get the 1density of the entire dump and hence the weight of the dump for the days. The average weight of waste in the waste bag and the average volume of the waste bag was taken to get the relation from density. The weights of the samples collected were recorded to estimate the solid waste generated in the Otuoke

A total of 250kg of waste were analyzed from the different dumpsites with 25 random samples throughout the study sites at 5 random sampling for each dumpsite. The waste was then placed on the already spread large tarp and a

representative 5000g sample size was separated using the scale for sorting into different classifications of the solid waste. The identified and segregated items are sorted into the designated bags. In the case of composite items found in the waste, the individual materials were separated and placed in the appropriate storage bags. After sorting, the storage bags containing the waste were weighed and recorded according to the classifications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 sampled solid wastes collected from 5dumpsites

DAY	W.W (Kg)	V.M (M ³)	SITE 1		SITE 2		SITE 3		SITE 4		SITE 5					
			V.D M ³	D.D Kg/m ³	W.W (Kg)	VD (M ³)	D.D (Kg/m ³)	W.W (Kg)	V.D (M ³)	D.D (Kg/m ³)	W. W (Kg)	V.D (M ³)	D.D (Kg/m ³)			
1	1	0.13	1.8	112	196	1.5	96	144	1.6	50	79	1.5	96	140	1.7	96
2	1	0.13	2.3	324	128	1.8	115	64	1.5	46	70	1.2	88	104	1.2	120
3	1	0.13	2.8	176	160	2.2	137	88	1.4	55	77	1.2	74	156	1.4	88
4	1	0.13	3.1	199	139	2.8	176	188	1.4	50	70	1.2	112	156	1.4	124
5	1	0.13	3.4	214	95	3.0	191	84	1.6	51	77	1.2	76	90	1.4	130

V.D = VOLUME OF DUMP

D.D= DENSITY OF DUMP

W.W= WEIGHT OF WASTE

Using the correlation of density to volume of both waste bag and dump the estimated weight of the dump with respect to individual characterization of the waste

$$\frac{\text{density of dump}}{\text{density of waste bag}} = \frac{\text{volumme of dump}}{\text{volumme of waste bag}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Density of the dump becomes:

$$\text{Density of dump} = \frac{\text{volumme of dump} \times \text{density of bag}}{\text{volumme of waste bag}} \quad \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Hence, the weight of dumpsite = Density of dump X Volume of the dump. For subsequent consecutive days, the weight of waste at the dump will be the reduction from the previous day's waste

$$\text{Weight of waste for Day } (i) = \text{Total Weight } (i) - \text{Total Weight } (i-1)$$

Where i is the number of days from day 1 to 5

QUANTITY OF WASTE GENERATION

Table 1, gives the representation of the waste generated in Otuoke within the research period when the community is having its maximum population because the students of federal university Otuoke are in session which means the community is at its full capacity. The total weight of waste generated from the sample collection as reported in table 1, can be obtained as the Net Total weight of waste produced which is calculated as Σ_n which is 3083 kg; where n is the weight of waste (W.W) for dumpsites 1,2,3,4 and 5. Then the average waste produced per day is 616.6 kg which is generated from the five major dumpsites found miles apart with a very little number of people depositing their waste at these dumpsites because of the dumping patterns within the confines of Otuoke as a survey carried out in Otuoke metropolis shows other secondary dumpsites at strategic locations are rampant at different vicinities of the town and dumping of refuse inside the river, burning of waste is noticed, and sampled interview about waste disposal conducted randomly across Otuoke shows that an estimation of about 20% of the entire population of Otuoke dump their wastes at these five dumpsites which is 3608 people out of 18040 people Hence, deposited per person $(3083 / 3608) = 0.85\text{kg/capita/day}$ which fall within the range Waste generation rate in Nigeria that is estimated at 0.65 – 0.95 kg/capita/day [14] . Due to incriminate disposal of wastes noticed, the general public should be sensitized to the effect of improper management of solid waste, and policy should also be put in place and implement regulations that would stop improper disposal of waste. Otuoke community and the university community properly map out adequate dumpsites and should direct their efforts towards making projections future

to cater to the new and existing settlements to accommodate the possible increase in the volume of waste generated the future.

Table 2: Waste Characterization of 250kg Sample in Otuoke

DAYS	DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3	DAY 4	DAY 5	TOTAL (GRAMS)	AVG WASTE	PERCENTAGE COMPOSITION (%)
TYPES OF WASTE								
ORGANIC WASTE IN (GRAMS)								
Wood	2891	1193	2700	6406	4830	18021	3604.2	7.21
Food waste	14524	16318	7170	8992	5534	55586	11117.2	22.23
Manure	3419	1257	5949	7334	2733	24608	4921.6	9.84
Garden Waste (Grasses)	3365	2347	8142	2576	2757	20281	4056.2	8.11
TOTAL	24200	21115	23961	25308	14374	118496	23699.2	47.39
INORGANIC WASTE IN (GRAMS)								
Tin/metals	3345	2122	6947	18912	2930	17239	3447.8	6.89
Glass	2920	5972	1720	2908	710	14230	2846	5.68
Paper	2596	1832	1462	1112	6172	13174	2634.8	5.26
Hair	2672	1038	658	808	700	5876	1175.2	2.35
Rubber/Plastic	10624	11552	8804	7650	8432	47062	9412.4	18.82
Polythene	1840	3632	1648	7940	1246	16306	3261.2	6.52
Baby Diapers	450	600	3084	408	414	4956	991.2	1.98
Battery	375	300	636	471	600	2382	476.4	9.52
Hospital Waste	300	294	252	222	900	1968	393.6	0.78
Foam/Floater	675	1546	828	615	4644	8308	1661.6	3.32
TOTAL	25800	28888	26039	24232	26748	131504	26300.8	52.61

CHARACTERIZATION OF SOLID WASTE

Categorization of the Solid Waste

The percentage composition was gotten from the study period can be projected to give a certain characterization of waste for the entire weight of dump in Otuoke. As seen in Table 2, the waste in Otuoke is categorized into two major classifications namely; Organic Waste and Inorganic waste. Organic waste is the solid waste that contains an organic compound that can easily decompose, from the sampled waste is collected and cumulated in table 2, the following make up organic waste; wood, food waste, manure, and garden waste, while the inorganic waste includes; tin/metal, glass, paper, hair, rubber/plastic, polythene, baby diapers, battery, hospital waste. [15] The organic waste from the 250kg of waste studied was lower than the inorganic matter as indicated in table 2 where the organic waste has a total weight of 118.496kg with 47.39% as compared to inorganic waste with a total weight of 131.504kg and 52.61%. It can be deduced that Otuoke consumes more manufactured materials since it generates more inorganic

waste than organic because of its demographic nature with a high density of the student, and the community will require a recycling processing industry cited close for effective management of the solid waste.

Fig 8: Percentage Composition of Characterized Solid waste

However, figure 8 shows that food waste has the highest waste generated with 22.23% of all the samples collected and categorized, though food waste is classified as organic waste, it further affirms that restaurants make more sales because of the population of the student in Otuoke. Hospital waste which is classified as inorganic waste is the least with 0.78%. The food waste, manure, and garden waste can be properly managed to make organic manure for the production of crops

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ORGANIC WASTE COMPOSITION

Fig 9a: Organic Waste Composition

INORGANIC WASTE COMPOSITION

Fig. 9b: Inorganic Waste Composition

Organic waste

Food waste forms the highest percentage of all the categories of waste in general and organic waste in particular; this is majorly generated from dumpsites 1 and 2, where there are several restaurant food vendors with families that cook and dispose of the waste, this is in agreement with what happened in University of Lagos, Akoka Campus, as reported by [16], where the food waste compose the highest percentage (66.67%) than other organic waste, however food waste is low in Federal University Otuoke's hostel's dumpsite, because the student is not permitted to cook in the hostel, but rather move to the community and purchase their food. Moreover, Fig 9a shows the partner of the Characterized wastes in this category where food waste is the highest of all the four waste collected for the 5days of collection except the 3rd day where Garden is the highest because the samples were collected after the Bayelsa State Environmental Sanitation since the community is mostly agrarian, cut grasses, lawn, clearing of vegetation and fallen leaves from trees which makes up the Garden waste were more at the dumpsites. Garden waste makes up 1% of the total waste generated and wood is the least characterized organic waste with 7.21%, where Manure is 9.84 % highest after food waste as shown in Table 2 and reflected in Figure 8, which means endemic fertilizer can be manufacture from this waste.

Inorganic Waste

The most prominent waste from the inorganic section was rubber and plastic this may be because of the regular use of these items by students and the school. The Fig 9a shows that plastics have the highest inorganic waste in Otuoke with a total al weight of 47.062kg and 18.82% of the total collected samples. Plastics include household materials like broken chairs, buckets, plates, cooking utensils and spoons, bottles for packing water, soft drinks, and liquors, these have great economic value because plastics or rubber can be collected recycled. Tins/metals follow the plastics or rubber with 6.89% this may behave reduced because, the scavengers have a collecting point close to the community, and might have hunted for metals and tins all over the dumpsites in Otuoke toward transmission to their collecting point for recycling. The least of the inorganic waste is Baby Diapers which is 1.98%. Polythene has 6.52% of the inorganic waste; it is mostly used as wrapped for consumables, which can also be recycled like plastic since it cannot be decomposed. The quantity of the characterized IW collected per day must be noted here where rubber/ plastic is the highest among the IW in only days of sample collection except the 4th, but with high representation in on the day days collection. Tin/metal is the highest on the 4th day which may mean that the scavengers have not picked the metal from the dumpsites on the day of collection.

CONCLUSION

The waste generation per capita has increased with the growing population, and consumption particularly in Otuoke, the attempt made to solve the waste problem by classifying the waste generated where food and plastic and rubber produce the highest amount of waste, compared to other organic and inorganic solid waste. Looking at the pattern of waste generated, Otuoke metropolis is a growing community because of the volume of organic waste generated which must be properly managed to avoid leachate that may pollute nearby soil and water resources. Inorganic waste like plastic tin/metal and polythene should be recycled and the Hospital waste should be managed on its own because it increases the risk of human noncontact hazardous and highly infectious waste products and exposes the entire population to several forms of environmental pollution. Otuoke is not properly mapped out with dumpsites with projections in anticipation of the growing population of the university community and Otuoke community.

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